

Physical Therapy Exercise Protocol for Chronic Low Back Pain: Synchronous Online Prescription

Larissa Passos Fonseca Bonassoli
Universidade Tecnológica Federal do
Paraná – UTFPR
Curitiba, Brazil
ORCID: 0009-0001-4249-4550

Leandra Ulbricht
Universidade Tecnológica Federal do
Paraná – UTFPR
Curitiba, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-9514-2938

Frieda Saicla Barros
Universidade Tecnológica Federal do
Paraná – UTFPR
Curitiba, Brazil
ORCID: 0000-0002-3962-1192

Abstract — Chronic low back pain is a leading cause of functional disability, impacting quality of life and limiting daily activities. Aiming to find effective and accessible therapeutic alternatives in contexts with limited in-person care, this pilot study investigated the effects of a 12-week physical therapy protocol on two participants: one treated in person and the other through synchronous online sessions. Assessments included muscle strength, flexibility, pain-related functionality (Roland-Morris), postural control, and static stabilometry (Baropodometry). The online participant had a 75% reduction in functional disability (Roland-Morris from 8 to 2), increased flexibility (30 cm to 42.5 cm in the "Sit and Reach" test), abdominal strength (29 to 46 repetitions), and handgrip strength (26 kg to 51 kg). The in-person participant reduced functional disability by 66.67% (Roland-Morris from 12 to 4), increased flexibility (20.5 cm to 33 cm), abdominal strength (25 to 36 repetitions), and handgrip (22 kg to 47 kg). In stabilometry, the online participant presented changes in the COP position, with a lateral displacement of 0.1 mm to -1.7 mm and anteroposterior displacement of -3.0 mm to -3.4 mm, indicating postural reorganization. The average displacement velocity decreased from 11.1 mm/s to 9.7 mm/s, suggesting greater postural control. The in-person participant had changes in the COP position (X from -3.4 mm to 0.0 mm and Y from -4.3 mm to -5.3 mm) and a reduction in displacement velocity from 6.7 mm/s to 6.6 mm/s, maintaining stable postural control. These results suggest that the online protocol may be an effective alternative for telerehabilitation of patients with chronic low back pain, promoting significant improvements in function and postural control.

Keywords — chronic low back pain, online exercises, pilot study, physiotherapy, baropodometer.

I. INTRODUCTION

Low back pain is a leading cause of disability worldwide, affecting approximately 570 million people globally [1, 2]. Approximately 39% of the adult population will experience low back pain at some point during their lifetime [3]. It is estimated that among young adults (under 45 years of age), 3–4% become chronically disabled due to low back pain, while for older adults (over 45 years of age), this rate can range between 5–7% [4].

Low back pain refers to pain or discomfort that occurs in the region below the costal margin and above the upper buttock line, and may or may not be accompanied by pain radiating to the lower limb. It is considered chronic when it persists for more than 12 weeks [5, 6]. In these cases, symptoms are often associated with muscle imbalances, postural changes, and psychosocial components [7]. Given this multifactorial profile, non-pharmacological interventions, such as physical activity, have been widely recommended as the first line of treatment.

Physical therapy exercises are recognized as an effective approach for managing chronic low back pain, with benefits ranging from voluntary contraction of specific muscle groups to improved neurocoordination and postural stabilization. Such interventions aim to increase muscle and joint strength, improve range of motion, and optimize muscle function, resulting in pain reduction, improved function, and accelerated patient recovery, allowing them to return to normal activities. Furthermore, they can contribute to improved emotional and psychological well-being, which can also positively influence pain reduction and increased functionality [7, 8].

After the COVID-19 pandemic, online interactions increased in both work and social life, which also reflected in therapeutic approaches. Studies have associated supervised online exercises with significant results in various contexts, such as in people with hemophilia [9], patellofemoral pain syndrome [10], improved quality of life for workers [11], and pregnant women [12], and even demonstrated weight loss in participants in this modality [13].

This option of online activities can also favor increased access, especially in remote areas, and savings on travel. [14, 15, 16].

However, although there are studies demonstrating effective online interventions, two critical gaps persist: (a) the scarcity of accessible (equipment-free) online protocols for non-specific chronic low back pain (NSLBP), and (b) the scarcity of studies using objective methods to evaluate the results of these online protocols, as most are based on subjective questionnaires [17, 18].

Thus, this study aims to develop and evaluate a physiotherapeutic exercise protocol aimed at the treatment of chronic non-specific low back pain (CNSLP), which can be applied both in person and synchronously online, without the need for equipment, using exclusively body weight.

II. METHODOLOGY

A descriptive study was conducted involving physical therapy sessions provided in two distinct formats: one participant received in-person care and the other in synchronous online sessions, with real-time interaction via video call. Both participants were female: the in-person participant was 46 years old and the synchronous online participant was 43 years old. The physical therapy exercise program lasted 12 weeks, with 50-minute sessions held twice a week, totaling 20 hours of physical exercise. This research was approved by the Human Research Ethics Committee under consolidated opinion number 7,073,509.

A. Measuring Instruments

Participants were assessed in person before and after the physical therapy program. Initially, a medical history was taken, followed by the administration of the Roland-Morris Disability Questionnaire (RM), which aims to assess functional limitations associated with low back pain.

Then, the following physical assessments were conducted with classification criteria compatible with the female sex and age group of the participants:

- **Muscle Flexibility:** Lumbar and hamstring flexibility were assessed using the "Sit and Reach" test using the Wells bench. The classification followed the criteria: < 24 cm (needs improvement), 25–29 cm (fair), 30–33 cm (good), 34–37 cm (very good), and > 38 cm (excellent) [19].
- **Muscle Strength:** Dynamic strength tests were applied to abdominal muscles, upper limbs (push-ups), and lower limbs (horizontal thrust). Abdominal strength was assessed by the number of repetitions in 1 minute: ≤ 16 (poor), 17–21 (below average), 22–25 (average), 26–30 (above average), ≥ 31 (excellent) [20]. In push-ups: ≤ 4 (weak), 5–10 (below average), 11–14 (average), 15–23 (above average), ≥ 24 (excellent) [21]. In horizontal thrust: < 1.30 m (very weak), 1.30–1.39 m (weak), 1.40–1.49 m (fair), 1.50–1.59 m (good), > 1.60 m (excellent) [22].
- **Handgrip:** Grip strength was measured with the Jamar Hand Dynamometer and was classified for women as follows: ≤ 54 kg (poor), 55–58 kg (below average), 59–64 kg (average), and 65–72 kg (above average) [19].
- **Postural Stability:** Stabilometry was performed with a baropodometer (EPS-R1, Kinetec), evaluating the center of pressure (COP) and postural sway in bipedal support with eyes open. The equipment is recognized for its accuracy in analyzing postural stability and is widely used in physical therapy to assess balance and prevent falls [23–26] — aspects particularly relevant in CLNSD, due to the associated muscle imbalances and postural changes [5, 7].

B. Description of the Exercise Protocol

A physical therapy exercise protocol was developed for DLCNE, focusing on activating the stabilizing muscles of the lumbar spine. The program included strength, mobility,

balance, flexibility, and motor control exercises performed exclusively with body weight, without the use of equipment. The sessions were structured in three phases: warm-up, targeted exercises, and cool-down. The exercise progression respected the participants' functional capacity, with gradual increases in complexity based on individual performance. This same protocol was applied to both in-person and synchronous online sessions, being developed to allow application in both modalities.

C. Digital Tool for Real-Time Supervision

The video calling tool selected for implementing the online exercise sessions was WhatsApp, with video calls conducted via personal mobile devices, both for the online participant and the researcher. The choice of this application was based on the participant's accessibility and familiarity with the platform, as well as its ease of use and availability of real-time connection. This allowed for supervision of the exercises and direct interaction between the participant and the researcher.

The analysis of the data from both participants included position measurements in the physical test classifications, in addition to the quantitative measurements obtained by the baropodometer, such as center of pressure (COP) and displacement speed.

III. RESULTS

The results obtained were organized based on the assessments carried out throughout the study, as presented in Table 1, which includes the results of the physical tests and questionnaires.

The data presented in Table 1 indicate improvements in all tests performed in both the in-person and online groups. A trend toward improvement in flexibility, muscle strength, and functionality parameters was observed in both participants. The variations in results suggest that the protocol produced positive effects in both formats.

In the 'Sit and Reach' test, the in-person participant went from 20.5 cm (rated as 'needs improvement') to 33 cm (rated as 'good'), representing a 60.98% improvement. The online participant, who started at 30 cm ('good'), reached 42.5 cm ('excellent'), representing a 41.67% improvement.

Regarding sit-ups, the in-person participant increased from 25 to 36 repetitions, a 44% improvement, while the online participant increased from 29 to 46 repetitions, a 58.62% increase. Push-ups, which the in-person participant started with just 2 repetitions (classified as 'weak'), increased to 20 repetitions ('above average'). The online participant, who started with 0, reached 25 repetitions.

Table 1. Comparative results of in-person and online participants, assessed pre- and post-intervention.

Test	In-Person Activity		Online Activity	
	Pre	Post	Pre	Post
1	20.5 Needs improvement	33 Good	30 Good	42.5 Exc.
2	25 Average	36 Exc.	29 Above average	46 Exc.
3	02 Weak	20 Above average	0 Weak	25 Exc.
4	85 Very weak	94 Very weak	90 Very weak	107 Very weak
5	22 Precarious	47 Precarious	26 Precarious	51 Precarious
6	12	04	8	2

The "Test" column indicates: 1 = Sit and Reach Test (lower back and hamstring flexibility, in cm); 2 = Sit-ups (maximum repetitions in 1 minute); 3 = Push-ups (maximum repetitions in 1 minute); 4 = Horizontal thrust (lower limb strength, in cm); 5 = Handgrip strength (kg/F); 6 = Roland-Morris Questionnaire (pain/disability score).

Other tests also showed improvements. Horizontal thrust increased from 85 cm to 94 cm in the in-person participant (+10.59%) and from 90 cm to 107 cm in the online participant (+18.89%). Handgrip strength also improved significantly in both participants, with the in-person participant increasing from 22 kg to 47 kg (+113.64%) and the online participant from 26 kg to 51 kg (+96.15%).

The Roland-Morris questionnaire, which measures disability, indicated a reduction in both participants, with the in-person participant showing a 66.67% improvement (from 12 to 4 points) and the online participant an improvement of 75% (from 8 to 2 points).

A. Center of Pressure (COP) and Static Stabilometry

Both participants demonstrated changes in the mean center of pressure (COP) position over the 12-week intervention period. The in-person participant showed a mean X-axis shift of -3.4 mm to 0 mm, while the online participant varied from 0.1 mm to -1.7 mm, suggesting changes in the oscillation pattern as shown in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1 – Displacement of the center of pressure (COP) of the online participant before the application of the physical therapy exercise protocol. Images obtained by static baropodometry in bipedal support with eyes open, during postural balance assessment.

A reduction in COP oscillation was observed after the intervention, with an average displacement on the X-axis decreasing from 0.1 mm (A) to -1.7 mm (B). The assessment was performed with the eyes open, without changing the support surface.

Furthermore, the online participant's postural stability index indicated a slight improvement, evidenced by a reduction in the average COP displacement speed from 11.1 mm/s to 9.7 mm/s. Although the gains were more pronounced in the in-person participant, the online participant's data also point to improvements in postural control.

Figure 2 – Displacement of the center of pressure (COP) of the online participant after the physical therapy exercise protocol.

DISCUSSION

The results of this pilot study indicate that the online protocol may be a viable strategy for promoting strengthening and flexibility in the treatment of chronic low back pain. Compared to existing literature, the present study observed improvements in the Roland-Morris Disability Index, with a 75% reduction in functional disability for the online participant and 66.67% for the in-person participant. These findings are consistent with the results of an analysis of 19 randomized controlled trials with 1,108 participants, which reported an average reduction of 2.26 points on the Roland-Morris Disability Questionnaire [27]. Furthermore, another study that reviewed eight studies on physical therapy exercises reported a significant improvement in functional disability, with an average reduction of 5.46 points on the Roland-Morris [28]. The results indicate a positive trend in all cases, suggesting that the protocol proposed in this study

may have a positive impact, similar to that observed in larger studies.

This positive impact may be directly related to core stabilization, through strengthening the deep abdominal and lumbar muscles, improving postural support, and reducing compensatory movements. This process involves the integration of passive, active, and neural systems, with neuromuscular control playing a crucial role in this process [29]. Furthermore, strengthening and stretching the hamstring muscles have been linked to improved postural control and dynamic balance in patients with chronic low back pain. A randomized trial showed that, for patients with hamstring tightness, static stretching exercises had a more significant effect on improving balance than muscle strengthening exercises, especially in the anterior direction [30]. Improved balance is directly related to postural stability, reducing overload on spinal structures and avoiding movements that can exacerbate pain. The ability to maintain adequate dynamic balance reflects the correct activation of stabilizing muscles, including the core muscles, which helps preserve posture and functionality during daily activities [31].

The use of a baropodometer as an assessment tool allowed an objective analysis of the protocol's impact. The reduction in center of pressure (COP) oscillation indicated greater stability during static posture, suggesting an improvement in postural balance. These findings, which include not only improved muscle strength but also improved postural adaptation among participants, indicate that the protocol may have contributed to a functional reorganization of plantar load distribution and postural control. The literature supports the use of the baropodometer as an effective tool for postural and biomechanical analysis, especially in individuals with low back pain [23, 32].

However, not all studies have found significant changes in this variable. For example, in one clinical trial, even after 20 rehabilitation or stretching sessions, no improvements were observed in static baropodometry, suggesting that the type of population, exercise modality, and protocol duration may directly influence outcomes related to static balance and plantar pressure distribution [25].

In the online mode, although the improvements were more moderate compared to the in-person mode, the results indicated benefits in postural control, evidenced by the reduction in center of pressure (COP) sway in static stabilometry with eyes open. Although there are not many studies that specifically use static stabilometry in telerehabilitation protocols for low back pain, our findings are in line with the literature associating postural deficits with chronic low back pain [33].

Improving postural balance is important for functionality (reducing symptoms) and preventing falls. Furthermore,

studies on telerehabilitation have demonstrated relevant functional gains, even in the absence of continuous in-person supervision (present in this study), indicating the viability of the online method [34].

As this was a pilot study, preliminary results indicate that the developed protocol of physiotherapy exercises used online was effective in improving physical function and reducing chronic low back pain, offering a viable alternative for people with difficulty accessing in-person treatments.

The use of technologies such as WhatsApp to supervise online exercises has proven suitable for implementing a remotely supervised exercise protocol, ensuring that participants can perform physical therapy exercises safely. The feasibility and safety of digital platforms for musculoskeletal rehabilitation have been widely demonstrated in recent studies [9-16].

Among the limitations of this pilot study, the small sample size should be considered, which restricts the generalization of the findings.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This pilot study suggests that the physiotherapy exercise protocol developed specifically for chronic low back pain, applied both in person and online, promoted relevant functional improvements in people with CLBP.

The online participant stands out, as the protocol was developed specifically to verify the viability of this modality. She showed improvements in flexibility, abdominal muscle strength, and upper limb strength. Furthermore, there was a reduction in functional disability, indicating a significant improvement in performing daily activities.

Data indicated a reduction in center of pressure (COP) oscillation in the online participant, demonstrating improved postural control. Furthermore, both participants showed improvements in balance.

The application of the online protocol represented an accessible alternative for people who face difficulties in accessing in-person physiotherapy treatments, enabling effective interventions and remote monitoring by physiotherapists.

Future research consists of deepening the understanding of the benefits of associating abdominal muscle ultrasound with clinical evaluation and expanding the protocol with a larger group of participants.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We would like to thank the Federal Technological University of Paraná for the support and infrastructure provided for this study. We are also grateful to the participants, without whom this study would not have been possible.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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Author: Larissa Tainara Passos Fonseca
 Institute: Universidade Tecnológica Federal do Paraná - UTFPR
 Street: September 7th, 3165
 City: Curitiba
 Country: Brazil
 Email: larissapassosf@yahoo.com.br